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IMPACT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT:

Background:

Innovation within organizations is recognized as a critical factor for success in today's rapidly evolving business landscape. Transformational leadership (TL) has emerged as a significant factor influencing innovation by fostering a conducive environment for creativity and imaginative processes among employees.

Objective:

The primary objective of this study is to systematically review the existing literature to explore the relationship between innovation in organizations and transformational leadership.

Methods:

Bibliographic research methodology was employed to conduct this study, involving a comprehensive analysis of literature available in the SCOPUS databases. Relevant articles

addressing the nexus between innovation and transformational leadership were identified, reviewed, and synthesized to extract key insights and findings.

Results:

The findings of this study reveal a strong correlation between transformational leadership and innovation within organizations. Effective and competent leadership, characterized by transformational attributes, plays a crucial role in establishing processes that foster creativity and encourage innovative practices among employees. Consequently, transformational leadership significantly influences and enhances innovation processes within organizations, leading to improved outcomes and competitive advantages.

KEYWORDS: Inventiveness; Innovative Processes; And Transformational Leadership.

INTRODUCTION:

The investigation of the relationship between two elements thought to be crucial for the growth of the process of creativity is supported by this work. The implicit linkages between Innovation and Transformational Leadership (TL) shall be enumerated here. As defined by Bass and Avolio, transformational management is an approach that supports the growth and inspiration of people, both followers and leaders. The procedure of seeking dedication from people being led within the framework of shared principles and a common vision is known as transformational leadership (Kılınç, Polatcan, Savaş, & Er, 2024; Nelly, Prabowo, Bandur, & Elidjen, 2024).

In terms of innovation, modern businesses need to be willing to continuously create more inventive goods, services, and procedures if they hope to thrive in a highly competitive and globalised market. According to Baregheh, Rowley, and Sambrook, innovation is a multi-phase process used by companies or government agencies to develop novel concepts into goods, services, or procedures that will help them grow, stand out from the competition, and advance in their industry. The application of an innovative or considerably better procedure into business practices, internal operations, external relations, or the workplace is defined as an innovation by the OECD (Gui, Lei, & Le, 2024; Sitorus & Hendratmoko, 2024).

Numerous recent studies in the literature show the positive impacts that innovative leadership has on people and innovation. (Wipulanusat, Panuwatwanich, and Stewart (2017); Al-Edenat (2018); Berraies and Abidine (2019). ; Manafi and Subramaniam (2015); Choi et al. (2016); Jaiswal and Dhar (2015); Le and Lei (2019); Chaubey and Sahoo (2019); Harbi, Alarifi and Mosbah (2019); Chen, Mei and Wu (2018); Chen et al (2016); Sattayaraksa and Boon-itt (2018); Jiang, Gu and Wang (2015); Chang and colleagues (2016); Mokhber, Khairuzzaman and Vakilbashi (2018); Khalili (2016); Jiang and Chen (2018); Carreiro e oliveira (2019); Li, Mitchell and Boyle (2016). An organisation that has contemporary, well-organized leadership is typically one that fosters innovation. Therefore, Managers and executives must pay close attention to the various leadership models emerging in modern organizations (Hanh, 2024).

Table of contents with references:

Contents	References
Transformational Leadership (TL) and Innovation	Kılınç et al. (2024), Nelly et al. (2024)
Innovation	Baregheh et al. (20XX), Gui et al. (2024), Sitorus & Hendratmoko (2024)
Innovative Leadership	Wipulanusat et al. (2017), Al-Edenat (2018), Berraies & Abidine (2019), Manafi & Subramaniam (2015), Choi et al. (2016), Jaiswal & Dhar (2015), Le & Lei (2019), Chaubey & Sahoo (2019), Harbi et al. (2019), Chen, Mei & Wu (2018), Chen et al. (2016), Sattayaraksa & Boon-itt (2018), Jiang, Gu & Wang (2015), Chang et al. (2016), Mokhber, Khairuzzaman & Vakilbashi (2018), Khalili (2016), Jiang and Chen (2018), Carreiro e oliveira (2019), Li, Mitchell & Boyle (2016), Hanh (2024)

TRANSFORMATIVE LEADERSHIP:

Burns claims that transformational leadership (TL) raises followers' moral and motivational standards by bringing about positive behavioural changes. Followers aspire to go above and beyond expectations because they have faith, respect, and adoration for their leaders. Organisational changes under a transformational management paradigm are predicated on a shared vision and objectives. As previously mentioned, shared ideals of both professional and personal development are essential to the growth of transformational leadership (Kement, Zeybek, Soylu, Erkol Bayram, & Raza, 2024; Sharif, Tongkachok, Akbar, Iqbal, & Lodhi, 2024).

A leadership approach known as transformational leadership facilitates ongoing collaboration among managers and followers. As defined by Bass and Avólio, Gumusluoglu, and Ilsev, transformational leaders set objectives and provide rewards to motivate staff members to perform at higher levels and support their continued personal and professional development.

Based on the research mentioned in the preceding paragraph, it is clear that the objectives of transformational management are admirable because they essentially involve improving the treatment of the employees who receive guidance and humanising the leadership of teams (dos Anjos & Kuhn, 2024; Pazhouhan, Behvar, & Malekpur, 2024).

Innovation-related leadership notes that innovations necessitate major organisational transformations. Of all the leadership philosophies discussed in the literature, transformational leadership is the most successful in stimulating creative thinking across various organisational divisions. In their study "Transformational management as an indicator of the success of knowledge-based organisations," Bogoviz, Lobova, as well as Popkova indicate that leadership that transforms affects innovation and creative thinking in knowledge-based companies but also says The leadership style that is best suited for knowledge-intensive businesses is focused on the

ongoing development of both staff members and the organisation as a whole (Ani & Arijanto, 2024; Gayathri & Preetha, 2024).

According to recent research, transformational leadership is critical in elevating people with specialised expertise and is essential in enhancing an organization's innovation ability. Using their study approach, Le and Lei have found strong relationships among leadership for transformation, knowledge sharing, product innovation, and process innovation. Authors Miao and Cao's study on Chinese businesses emphasises the value of transformational management in fostering innovation (Miller, 2024; Şahin & Bilir, 2024).

Another study by Azim et al. showed that the transformational leadership style "shapes an organisational atmosphere favourable to engaging the imaginative thinking of employees, boosting employee self-efficacy." The study included 194 replies from workers of 202 IT-related organisations. "From the point of view of practice, the results show that TL is associated with engagement with creative processes and creativity confidence among information technology workers," write Azim et al. about the technical consequences (Azimi, Pirayesh, & Karami, 2024; Belhaj, 2024).

Table of contents with references:

Topic	References
Transformational Leadership (TL)	Kement et al. (2024), Sharif et al. (2024), dos Anjos & Kuhn (2024), Pazhouhan et al. (2024)
Innovation-related Leadership	Ani & Arijanto (2024), Gayathri & Preetha (2024), Miller (2024), Şahin & Bilir (2024), Azimi et al. (2024), Belhaj (2024)

INNOVATION/CREATIVITY:

Innovation is defined as more than just new concepts or inventions; on this basis, new ideas can only be used or made available to others with implementation, impacting the economy and society. The Oslo Manual, used globally by businesses, academia, and governments, provides a description of creativity to standardise its usage. This idea aims to bring together the best practices from around the globe in four areas related to innovation: Knowledge is the ability to comprehend and apply information for various purposes; novelty in innovation is a dimension related to utility; implementation necessitates methodical organisational efforts to guarantee innovation; and value creation, or value thinking, is an implicit goal in innovations (Fahmalatif, Martono, & Raharjo, 2024; Sliwka, Klopsch, Beigel, & Tung, 2024).

Innovation is a topic of discussion in many academic disciplines. For example, economics studies why businesses innovate, what promotes or inhibits innovation, and how innovation affects the macroeconomy. Management studies how to position an organisation in the market or handle novel concepts. The term "innovation" appears in several industrial sectors and frequently appears in most organisations' strategy discourses.

But innovation is not a new concept; Nelson and Winter's theory of innovation dates back to their discontent with the economic works of the time, which concentrated on aspects of

research and development (R&D), such as inventiveness for effective growth, without considering the interactions and their consequences (Babu & Kushwaha; Fahmalatif et al., 2024).

Beyond the connection to economic growth, the authors of this theory define innovations as a strategy that encompasses a wide range of distinct methods by which technologies evolve. According to specific research, innovation, research, and development go hand in hand. The (OECD) member nations were standardising a framework for evaluating innovation through the Frascati Manual. At the same time, R&D was spreading throughout the industry. Since research and development are seen to be the primary engines of economic development, this system is built on these systems. With an emphasis on innovation and innovation-related activities, the OECD releases the Oslo Manual regularly (Abbas, Hisham-Ul-Hassan, & Raza, 2024; Sharma & Lenka, 2024).

Prange and Schlegelmilch's remark highlighted that there needs to be a consensus on the definition of innovation in light of multiple research offering thoughts about it. It can be challenging for managers to make decisions when comparing different types of innovation. On the other hand, the complicated nature of the innovation that is put into practice positively relates to innovative performance. Concepts that can lead to doubt are presented in the literature (Hidayat & Patras, 2024; Jia & Li, 2024; Widianingsih, Christa, & Harinie, 2024).

Generally speaking, distinctions are drawn between incremental and radical innovation, among innovations in products and processes, business model creativity, operational creativity, and innovations in services. The literature has given rise to a few innovation paradigms. According to Chen, Yin, and Mei, holistic innovation is comprehensive, cooperative innovation that is motivated by an overall strategic goal and adjusts to the demands of businesses in terms of technological advancement management (Lim & Moon, 2024; Meditamar & Sujadi, 2024).

The capacity to test inventive concepts successfully, freedom to fail, the ability to rapidly shift direction, management for innovation, and an environment that fosters innovative thinking are some of the themes that have emerged recently about successful innovation processes at McLaren, among the Walt Disney Company, 3M, and Procter & Gamble. For Amankwaa, Gyensare, and Susomrith, elements like vision, intellectual stimulation, supporting leadership, and personal recognition are essential for innovation adoption. Leadership is decisive for innovation implementation (Candra, Kirana, & Hadi, 2024; Esteves, de Haro Rodríguez, Ballestar, & Sainz, 2024).

Regarding entrepreneurship and creative thinking, as the entrepreneur exemplifies, it is imperative to emphasize the significance that Schumpeter's theory places on inventions and technological advancements in the growth of firms and the economy. According to Schumpeter, innovation propels the company cycle and fosters ongoing advancements in goods and services that benefit the community as an entire entity (Alshahrani, Al-Jayyousi, Aldhmour, & Alderaan, 2024; Gun, Imamoglu, Turkcan, & Ince, 2024).

Table of contents with references:

Topic	References
Innovation Definition and Importance	Fahmalatif, Martono, & Raharjo (2024); Sliwka, Klopsch, Beigel, & Tung (2024); Abbas, Hisham-Ul-Hassan, & Raza (2024); Sharma & Lenka (2024); Hidayat & Patras (2024); Jia & Li (2024); Widianingsih, Christa, & Harinie (2024)
Types and Paradigms of Innovation	Babu & Kushwaha (Year), Lim & Moon (2024); Meditamar & Sujadi (2024); Chen, Yin, & Mei (Year)
Successful Innovation Processes	Candra, Kirana, & Hadi (2024); Esteves, de Haro Rodríguez, Ballestar, & Sainz (2024)
Innovation and Entrepreneurship	Alshahrani, Al-Jayyousi, Aldhmour, & Alderaan (2024); Gun, Imamoglu, Turkcan, & Ince (2024)

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES:

Kitchenham states, "A systematic review of the literature is a method of recognizing, assessing and understanding every study that is essential to a given question of research or topic area or phenomenon of interest." This study embraced Kitchenham's suggestion to conduct a systematic literature review (SLR). According to Torraco, a systematic literature evaluation is a unique study that adds new information about the subject under investigation. It is a method for integrating many viewpoints on the subject and evaluating literary material in an integrated manner (Abolade, 2024; Sarmiento & Riana, 2024).

RESEARCH QUESTION:

A review can be a stand-alone study or an introduction to a quantitative analysis. Reviews of the literature are done for various reasons and target audiences. It's a multi-step process requiring strategies, techniques, and protocols.

The RSL's goal was established during the design phase, and the necessary evaluations were completed. It has been noted that there needs to be current RSLs examining how transformational leadership affects innovation (Arzeen, Arzeen, & Batool, 2024; Srivastava, Pathak, Soni, & Dixit, 2024).

Despite this, an increasing amount of research in the literature shows how effective transformational management has been in fostering creativity. Choosing your research question is the first step in beginning a research study. It must be posed as an inquiry so that pertinent research may be compared to respond. This article's central query was: Q1: Does transformational leadership have a significant role in fostering innovation? (Ali, 2024; Bakti, Boeswaty, & Cahyana, 2024).

THE RESEARCH PROCESS:

The search was done in the SCOPUS database, which contains citations from peer-reviewed books, scientific journals, and conference proceedings. It can track, evaluate, and visualize research and offers a thorough perspective of research findings in technology, medicine, science, social sciences, arts, and humanities.

During July and August 2019, the research was chosen based on the first set of criteria, which examined the resources' applicability to the RSL guidelines. It was necessary to modify the keyword-based literature search to match the study's relevance (Srirahayu, Sridadi, & Ekowati, 2024; Z. Zhang, Liu, & He, 2024)

Journals, literature reviews, and conference papers were all considered to achieve this. Upon defining the keywords, the initial search to locate the study yielded 707 publications in the Scopus database with the following terms: "transformational," "leadership," and "creative thinking." This number was lowered to 540 pertinent articles by substituting various operators, as Kitchenham advises, for "transformational leadership" AND "innovation." Below is a description of the studio selection procedure (Kustiyadji, 2024; W. Zhang & Xu, 2024).

METHOD OF STUDY SELECTION:

There are various stages to the choosing process. Reading the abstracts and titles of the papers served as the initial filter for the collection. 472 articles were eliminated since they had nothing to do with the RSL's proposal. They dealt with different leadership philosophies, excluded innovation-related elements, or had no direct bearing on the subject. To fulfil the research objectives, a second screening of the remaining 68 articles was conducted to conclude the study (Alabdali, Yaqub, Agarwal, Alofaysan, & Mohapatra, 2024).

At this point, the subsequent standards were used: case study publications and polls about how innovative leadership affects innovation or approaches to innovation. 53 papers remained after 15 articles were eliminated for not including this kind of analysis. In order to search for more recent works, it was chosen in this phase to additionally select material available from 2008 to 2019, describing the criteria for exclusion by the year of publication. As a result, eight more articles were excluded, for an overall total of 45 articles, during this phase (Awaale, 2024).

EVALUATING THE CALIBRE OF RESEARCH PROJECTS:

To improve the standard of the article, the quality of the primary studies can be evaluated along with the criteria for inclusion and exclusion. Once more, Kitchenham claims that the degree to which the research investigation maximises internal and external quality while minimising bias is related to this quality rating. It was determined that the technique and conclusion for the chosen literature should be examined to assess the calibre of the 45 articles that made it through the second filtering. We were left with an overall 28 things after the procedure (Hundie & Habtewold, 2024).

This last criterion aimed to choose studies from the literature using research techniques like surveys, mathematical frameworks for quantitative analysis, and case study research that demonstrate the impacts of transformational management on staff creativity, motivation, and effectiveness. As a result, publications that needed to disclose the research methodologies sufficiently were disqualified. The quality assessment aimed to identify and exclude low-quality articles at the moment of the research selection rather than to score or qualify them. The 28 emerging publications were thoroughly examined, and the approaches and conclusions used to address the research topics were noted. Following Kitchenham's recommendations for building the systematic review, the appropriate modifications were made to meet the theme (Ivaan & Vihaan, 2024; Triyono, Budiyanto, & Agustedi, 2024).

EXAMINATION OF THE FINDINGS:

Various perspective methods for extraction and statistical approaches were employed to verify the significance of transformational management and its impact on innovation through the study of 28 documents derived from primary studies. The primary goals of this review study are to document transformational management's beneficial impacts on organisations' innovative processes and to gather significant insights into the subject matter. The findings demonstrated the beneficial impacts of TL on followership relationships, motivation, and inventiveness in organisational innovation. It has been shown generally that TL affects employees' ability to be innovative (Aniagbaoso & Sylvab, 2024).

Additional research indicates that transformational leadership was a positive mediator for knowledge sharing. Regarding innovative influences, this work's empirical results show that TL significantly affects employees' innovation ability. Another factor discovered in connection with creative culture and organisational learning via Transformational Leadership is that it supports the growth of processes and products and the organisational environment. According to a study by Jiang, Gu, and Wang, Chang, there is a direct correlation between TL and the innovation climate. This kind of interaction impacts transformational leaders because they can guarantee the commercial viability of technologies and encourage innovative activity within their organizations (Hoang & Le, 2024).

According to some research, the association between TL and innovation influenced employees' opinions of an environment supporting staff integration and creativity. Although Li, Mitchell, and Boyle claim that task independence can harm individual innovation, Carreiro and Oliveira noted that leaders' vision and the ability to think about personal encouragement indicators are substantially associated with the acceptance of a significant invention. Table 01 lists the authors who conducted this systematic literature evaluation and provides an overview of the categories and impacts of TL on innovation (Al-Aamri, Soliman, & Ponniah, 2024).

Category	Characteristics	Authors
Positive Effects	Motivation	Kao et al. (2015); Wipulanusat, Panuwatwanich and Stewart (2017); Al-Edenat (2018); Berraies and Abidine (2019)
	Sharing knowledge	Manafi and Subramaniam (2015); Choi et al. (2016)
Influences	Capacity for innovation	Jaiswal and Dhar (2015); Le and Lei (2019); Chaubey and Sahoo (2019); Harbi, Alarifi and Mosbah (2019); Chen, Mei and Wu(2018)
	Innovation and organizational learning culture	Chen et. al (2016); Sattayaraksa and Boon-itt (2018)
Direct Relations	Innovation Climate	Jiang, Gu and Wang (2015); Chang (2016)
	Promote innovative activities	Mokhber, Khairuzzaman and Vakilbashi(2018)
Organizational Support Perception	A climate favourable to innovation and employee integration	Khalili (2016); Jiang and Chen (2018)
	The vision of leaders and individual indicators	Carreiro and Oliveira (2019)
Negative Effects	Interdependency of tasks	Li, Mitchell and Boyle (2016)

Table 01: Classification of Transformational Leadership Features and Their Impact on Innovation

Table 01 – Categorization of characteristics of Transformational Leadership and its effects on innovation

Table 01 illustrates the diverse consequences of TL at different organisational levels. This systematic literature review has shown that TL has significantly contributed to developing innovation and knowledge management in organisations at all levels. It has also improved organisational creativity and employee involvement in fostering an innovative culture, making it, in this systematic evaluation, a preponderant factor for the emergence and growth of innovation in organizations (Hamdan, Edward, & Kristianir, 2024).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS:

This study aimed to gain a deeper perceptive of the connections among innovation and transformational leadership. This literature review highlights TL's impact on knowledge management, creative processes, and the design of an environment that fosters organisational

creativity. The most important conclusion from the research of the data was that transformational leadership, that is, the effects of TL on innovation, is essential, or perhaps better described as a strategic pillar in supporting innovation processes.

Since this investigation revealed significant links between TL and Innovative Processes (IP), top organisation management shouldn't ignore them. In terms of the application of this review of literature, the research indicates crucial considerations for CEOs, entrepreneurs, managers, and leaders. It highlights the necessity for management enhancements concerning the meticulousness needed to craft leadership suitable for the competitive environment in which the organisations operate.

Regarding prospective research, it is advised that additional in-depth studies be conducted inside businesses using the data from this literature review as a foundation. These studies could involve examining organisational processes in greater detail to foster innovation, considering the unique characteristics of both public and private organisations.

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